

URBAN-WASTE – 690452 – D3.9

URBAN-WASTE

Urban strategies for Waste Management in Tourist Cities D3.9 – CoP Platform

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Abstract

The CoP platform represent within URBNAWASTE the virtual place for stakeholders’ engagement and discussion. The CoP platfrom will be integrated in the URBANWASTE website and will be organized in each pilot of the project and interaction will take thus place at local level. To create an EU added value out of this innovative experience in collectively-based policy making, a European room will be set up to allow and facilitate the exchange of information on the activities organized and proposals developed among the different local CoP. The e-platform will part of the website and will operate as a blog where representatives from the CoP and external organizations and individuals will be able to publish and share opinions, best practices and other information related with waste prevention and management and urban planning.

Contributors

The sole responsibility for the content of this report lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union. Neither EASME nor the European Commission are responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

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List of abbreviations

ACR+	Association of Cities and Regions for Recycling and Sustainable Resource management
CE	Consulta Europa
WP	Work Package
D	Deliverable
CoP	Communities of Practices

1. Communities of Practice (CoP) Platform

1.1 CoP Platform

The **Communities of Practice (CoP)** platform is included in the URBANWASTE website (<http://www.urban-waste.eu/>) and aims at facilitating the exchange of information on the activities organized and the proposals developed within each local CoP and among them. The platform will be thus composed of different “rooms”, each one dedicated to a specific CoP.

The Platform is included in the website under the menu ‘Mobilization and Mutual learning Plan’. The Figure below shows how this platform will look like on the website.

Fig. 1 CoP Platform on the URBANWASTE Website. The 11 pilots are represented by the 11 rooms.

The 11 pilots are here represented by 11 ‘rooms’. Participants and stakeholders of each local CoP will be invited to enter the platform and to include their vision and comments to the discussion raised by the local CoP administrator or by other stakeholders.

These will be the name of the rooms:

- CoP Ayuntamiento de Santander
- CoP City of Copenhagen
- CoP Cabildo de Tenerife
- CoP Kavala
- CoP Comune di Siracusa

- CoP DUNEA Dubrovnik – Neretva county
- CoP Lisbon
- CoP Metropole Nice Cote d’Azul
- CoP Ponta Delgada
- CoP Nicosia
- CoP Regione Toscana
- European CoP

Each local Cop “room” will be composed of:

- a forum (i.e. Test 2 in Fig.2) where CoP members will be able to discuss on specific topics proposed by them or by the CoP coordinator. The forum will allow members to share pictures and document.
- a section dedicated to “Events and news” will be foreseen to inform CoP members of activities related to the CoP itself or related to waste prevention and management activities and/or events.

Fig.2 CoP local Platform. Copenhagen’s test.

There will be a “European room” dedicated to foster exchange of information between members of a same CoP. This room will be composed only of the forum section.

Management of the European CoP will be centralised by the website admin, while within each local CoP room a COP coordinator will be nominated (look at section 1.2) who will have right to edit and post content on his local platform. Each individual page should be fed by news/posts and it will look like a blog in the end.

Fig.3 Forum Discussion- Test

Fig. 3 represent the design of each discussion where there is the possibility to leave comments related to that particular topic.

1.2 Cop Coordinator and responsible of the Platform

Each pilot nominates a responsible for the smooth running of the events organized within the local CoP. This person will also be the main facilitator of the CoP room of his pilot within the CoP Platform. The coordinator of each CoP room will be responsible to facilitate and keep the discussion on the platform lively. In the following table the responsible of each local CoP has been listed per pilot.

CoP COORDINATOR	PILOT PARTNER
Iva Pozniak	DUNEA
Alejandro Molowny; Carlos Diaz Rivero	CABILDO DE TENERIFE
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